

**THEORY OF OBJECTS' EMISSION IN CONDITIONS OF
NON-GEOMETRICAL OPTICS.**

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S u m m a r y

Interzone radiation from plane-parallel plate of direct-band-gap semiconductor is theoretically studied. The plate thickness in one direction is less or of the order of the radiation wave length. The system of characteristic nodes for radiation being emitted from such a plate is obtained. It is shown that the radiation has strongly marked radiation peaks for resonance transmission.

1. INTRODUCTION AND PURPOSE

Over prolonged periods the problem of investigation of cavity resonators radiation character for non-geometrical optics is still paid a significant attention.

Sufficiently complete overview of investigations in this field is given in [1] where different studies containing solutions in the form of infinite series with residual terms of different kinds are listed; also, the radiation of samples of different geometry is considered.

These results remain topical until present. As the appropriate review showed the works published afterwards don't comprise any significant supplementary information.

The aim of present article is to obtain analytically precise solution for the problem being discussed as applied to semiconductors which enables one to take properly into account the properties of a plane-parallel plate as a resonator.

The solution for the problem in case of different geometries may be found in a similar way.

2. PLANE-PARALLEL PLATE MODES

a) The system of modes

Transitions between two different states of a hole in the valence band under the secondary quantized radiation emission are represented by the Hamilton operator:

$$\hat{H} = -\frac{e}{2c} \left(\vec{V}_{\vec{p}} \vec{A}^{\vec{r}} + \vec{A}^{\vec{r}} \vec{V}_{\vec{p}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where

$$\vec{A}^{\vec{r}} = \sum_{\nu} \sqrt{\frac{2\pi\hbar c^2}{\omega_{\nu} V}} \left(\mathbf{b}_{\nu} \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}} + \mathbf{b}_{\nu}^{\dagger} \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}*} \right) \quad (1a)$$

Here the denotations are as follows:

$\vec{V}_{\vec{p}}$ - holes velocity operator; $\vec{A}^{\vec{r}}$ - secondary quantized vector potential; ω_{ν} - ν mode frequency; $\mathbf{b}_{\nu}^{\dagger} |b_{\nu}\rangle$ - Bose operator of creation (annihilation) for ν -mode; $\vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}}$ - describes the polarization characteristics and space structure for ν -mode; ν includes: μ - polarization index $|s, p|$. j -mode index $|r, l, L|$.

$\vec{q}_{\parallel}$ - longitudinal wave vector; the mode cross structure is determined by wave vectors - continuous ones $\vec{q}, \tilde{q}$ for l, r modes and discrete $\mathbf{k}$ - for L mode;

r, l, L - right, left and in-plate localized modes respectively; V - normalized volume.

As stated in [2], the modes system for the medium with dielectric constant $\epsilon^{\vec{r}}$ is derived from the following equations:

$$\text{rot rot } \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}} - \left(\frac{\omega_{\nu}}{c} \right)^2 \epsilon^{\vec{r}} \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{1}{V} \int_{(V)} d\vec{r} \epsilon^{\vec{r}} \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}*} \vec{a}_{\nu'}^{\vec{r}} = \delta_{\nu\nu'} \quad (2a)$$

which one should solve separately for S -polarization $|\text{div } \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}} = 0|$ and p -polarization $|\text{div } \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}} \neq 0|$.

In the one-dimensional case with inhomogeneous conditions being under consideration ($\vec{r} = (\vec{\tau}, x)$, $\vec{e}_x$ - normal to the plate) the solution for the system (2-2a) will be as follows:

$$\vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}} = \exp(i\vec{q}_{\parallel}\vec{\tau}) \left\{ \frac{[\vec{e}_x \times \vec{q}_{\parallel}]}{q_{\parallel}} a_{qx}^{\nu s} + \left[\vec{e}_x a_{qx}^{\nu p} + \frac{i\vec{q}_{\parallel}}{q_{\parallel}^2 \epsilon^x} \frac{d}{dx} \left(\epsilon^x a_{qx}^{\nu p} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (3)$$

where the first item represents the solution for S -polarization, and the second and the third ones - for p -polarization.

Let us consider only S -type solutions for which the scalar functions $a_{qx}^{v_s}$ are derived from the following equations:

$$\frac{d^2 a_{qx}^{v_s}}{dx^2} + \left[\left(\frac{\omega}{c} \right)^2 \varepsilon^x - q_{\parallel}^2 \right] a_{qx}^{v_s} = 0 \quad (3a)$$

$$\frac{1}{L} \int_{(L)} dx \varepsilon^x a_{qx}^{v_s *} a_{qx}^{v_s} = \delta_{v_s v_s'} \quad (3b)$$

where L - normalized length in x - direction.

b) Mode structure

For the piecewise-homogeneous medium wave equation is solvable for regions where $\varepsilon^x = const$. At jumps of ε^x the boundary conditions

$$\left. \frac{da_{qx}}{dx} \right|_{-0}^{+0} = 0, \quad a_{qx} \Big|_{-0}^{+0} = 0 \quad (4)$$

are used.

In order to find all the constants of the wave equation for stratified medium one need - in addition to the boundary conditions (BC) at all the jumps of ε^x - also two BC's at $\pm\infty$.

Types of solutions:

r - and l - solutions: the amplitude of right-incident (r) or left-incident (l) wave is given i.e. two BC's are set at $+\infty$ or $-\infty$.

L - solutions: localized modes for which $a_{qx}|_{-\infty}^{+\infty} = 0$.

$\vec{a}_V^r$ is continuous at jumps of ϵ^x (i.e. a_{qx}^{vs} and a_{qx}^{vp}

functions are continuous), but p -polarization-generated term

$\frac{i}{q_{\parallel}\epsilon^x} \frac{d}{dx} (\epsilon^x a_{qx}^{vp})$ has a jump at the interface.

Since the system (2-2a) is linear and homogeneous, one of the constants for L -solutions is not determined by BC and we obtain a dispersion equation.

Let us consider three-layers medium case:

$$\epsilon^x = \begin{cases} 1, x < 0 \\ \epsilon^s, 0 < x < d \\ \epsilon, d < x \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Solutions for the system (3a,b) we seek in the following form:

$$a_{qx} = \begin{cases} A_+ \exp(i\bar{q}x) + A_- \exp(-i\bar{q}x), x < 0 \\ a_+ \exp(ikx) + a_- \exp(-ikx), 0 < x < d \\ B_+ \exp(i\tilde{q}x) + B_- \exp(-i\tilde{q}x), d < x \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where wave vectors:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{q}^2 &= \left(\frac{\omega_v}{c} \right)^2 - q_{\parallel}^2 \\ k^2 &= \left(\frac{\omega_v}{c} \right)^2 \varepsilon^s - q_{\parallel}^2 \\ \tilde{q}^2 &= \left(\frac{\omega_v}{c} \right)^2 \varepsilon - q_{\parallel}^2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6a)$$

Using (4) at jumps of ε^x we obtain:

$$x=0$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A_+ + A_- &= a_+ + a_- \\ \bar{q}(A_+ - A_-) &= k(a_+ - a_-) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7a)$$

$$x=d$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_+ \exp(ikd) + a_- \exp(-ikd) &= B_+ \exp(i\tilde{q}d) + B_- \exp(-i\tilde{q}d) \\ k[a_+ \exp(ikd) - a_- \exp(-ikd)] &= \tilde{q}[B_+ \exp(i\tilde{q}d) - B_- \exp(-i\tilde{q}d)] \end{aligned} \quad (7b)$$

L -solution

System (7a,b) takes the form:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A &= a_+ + a_- \\ \bar{q}' A &= ik(a_+ - a_-) \\ B &= a_+ \exp(ikd) + a_- \exp(-ikd) \\ -\tilde{q}' B &= ik[a_+ \exp(ikd) - a_- \exp(-ikd)] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{q}' &= \sqrt{q_{\parallel}^2 - \left(\frac{\omega_v}{c}\right)^2} > 0 \\ \tilde{q}' &= \sqrt{q_{\parallel}^2 - \left(\frac{\omega_v}{c}\right)^2} \varepsilon > 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (8a)$$

From (8) we get a system of two equations for $\mathbf{a}_+$, $\mathbf{a}_-$ solvability condition of which leads us to dispersion equation:

$$\begin{vmatrix} \bar{q}' - ik & \bar{q}' + ik \\ -(\tilde{q}' + ik)\exp(ikd) & -(\tilde{q}' - ik)\exp(-ikd) \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (9)$$

From (9) we can obtain expression for discrete set of vectors $\mathbf{k}$:

$$-\frac{\bar{q}'\tilde{q}' - k^2}{k(\bar{q}' + \tilde{q}')} = \text{ctg } kd \quad (10)$$

When all the coefficients in (8) are expressed through $\mathbf{a}_+$, one may obtain:

$$a_{qx} = a_L \begin{cases} \frac{2ik}{ik+\bar{q}} \exp(\bar{q}' x), & x < 0 \\ \exp(ikx) + \frac{ik-\bar{q}'}{ik+\bar{q}} \exp(-ikx), & 0 < x < d \\ \left[\exp(ikd) + \frac{ik-\bar{q}'}{ik+\bar{q}} \exp(-ikd) \right] \exp[-\tilde{q}'(x-d)], & d < x \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $a_L \equiv a_+$.

l -solution

System (7a,b) will take form:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A_+ + A_- &= a_+ + a_- \\ \bar{q}(A_+ - A_-) &= k(a_+ - a_-) \\ a_+ \exp(ikd) + a_- \exp(-ikd) &= B_+ \exp(i\tilde{q}d) \\ k[a_+ \exp(ikd) - a_- \exp(-ikd)] &= \tilde{q}B_+ \exp(i\tilde{q}d) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (12)$$

When all the coefficients in (12) are expressed through a_+ and a new normalization constant $a_l = a_+ \exp(ikd)$ is introduced, one may obtain:

$$a_{qx} = a_l \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left[(\bar{q}+k) \exp(-ikd) + (\bar{q}-k) \exp(ikd) \frac{k-\tilde{q}}{k+\tilde{q}} \right] \frac{\exp(i\bar{q}x)}{2\bar{q}} \\ + \left[(\bar{q}-k) \exp(-ikd) + (\bar{q}+k) \exp(ikd) \frac{k-\tilde{q}}{k+\tilde{q}} \right] \frac{\exp(-i\bar{q}x)}{2\bar{q}}, \quad x < 0 \\ \exp[ik(x-d)] + \frac{k-\tilde{q}}{k+\tilde{q}} \exp[-ik(x-d)], \quad 0 < x < d \\ \frac{2k}{k+\tilde{q}} \exp[i\tilde{q}(x-d)], \quad d < x \end{array} \right. \quad (13)$$

r - solution

System (7a,b) will be:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} A_- = a_+ + a_- \\ -\bar{q}A_- = k(a_+ - a_-) \\ a_+ \exp(ikd) + a_- \exp(-ikd) = B_+ \exp(i\tilde{q}d) + B_- \exp(-i\tilde{q}d) \\ k[a_+ \exp(ikd) - a_- \exp(-ikd)] = \tilde{q}[B_+ \exp(i\tilde{q}d) - B_- \exp(-i\tilde{q}d)] \end{array} \right\} \quad (14)$$

When all the coefficients in (14) are expressed through a_- we obtain:

$$a_{qx} = a_r \begin{cases} \frac{2k}{k+\bar{q}} \exp(-i\bar{q}x), & x < 0 \\ \frac{k-\bar{q}}{k+\bar{q}} \exp(ikx) + \exp(-ikx), & 0 < x < d \\ \left[(\tilde{q}+k) \frac{k-\bar{q}}{k+\bar{q}} \exp(ikd) + (\tilde{q}-k) \exp(-ikd) \right] \frac{\exp[i\tilde{q}(x-d)]}{2\tilde{q}} \\ + \left[(\tilde{q}-k) \frac{k-\bar{q}}{k+\bar{q}} \exp(ikd) + (\tilde{q}+k) \exp(-ikd) \right] \frac{\exp[-i\tilde{q}(x-d)]}{2\tilde{q}}, & d < x \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where $a_r \equiv a_-$.

After substitution of expressions (11), (13), (15) in to the normalization condition (3b) we get constants a_L, a_l, a_r respectively.

3. EQUATION FOR PHOTON DENSITY ONE-PARTICLE MATRIX

In the problem under discussion we suppose the interaction between holes and the photons emitted by the holes during the transition from the heavy to the light part of energy spectrum to be weak.

According to [3], stationary quantum kinetic equation for one-particle matrix for photon density will be:

$$i \left(\omega_{\nu'} - \omega_{\nu} \right) N_{\nu\nu'} = L_{\nu\nu'}^{(p)} \{ N, f \} \quad (16)$$

where $L_{\nu\nu'}^{(p)} \{ N, f \}$ - collision operator.

Similarly, as presented in [4], in case of great distances equation (16) is transformed with respect to Wigner representation in to the following form:

$$\mathbf{v}_{\perp} \frac{\partial N_{\vec{q}_{\parallel}}^{jj'}}{\partial x} = L_R^{(p)} \quad (17)$$

where $L_R^{(p)}$ - relaxation mechanisms governing the process of photon attenuation beyond the d -layer (holes are localized within the layer with thickness $d \ll q_{\perp}^{-1}$).

Boundary condition for equation (17) is:

$$\mathbf{v}_{\perp} N_{\vec{q}_{\parallel}}^{jj'}(q_{\perp}, x) \Big|_0^d = L_{\vec{q}_{\parallel}, q_{\perp}}^{(p)jj'} \{f\} \quad (17a)$$

where the expression for non-diagonal (with respect to index j)

photon generation rate $L_{\vec{q}_{\parallel}, q_{\perp}}^{(p)jj'} \{f\}$ presented using dipole

approximation, for matrix transition element has the following form:

$$L_{\vec{q}_{\parallel}, q_{\perp}}^{(p)jj'} \{f\} = \frac{(2\pi e)^2 \hbar}{\omega_q V \varepsilon^s} \sum_{mn} \sum_{\vec{p}\vec{p}'} M_{q_{\perp}}^{jj'} \left(n\vec{p} \left| n' \vec{p}' \right. \right) f_{n\vec{p}} \left(1 - f_{n'\vec{p}'} \right) \delta \left(\varepsilon_{n'\vec{p}'} + \omega_q - \varepsilon_{n\vec{p}} \right), \quad (18)$$

$$M_{q_{\perp}}^{jj'} \left(n\vec{p} \left| n' \vec{p}' \right. \right) = \left(n\vec{p} \left| \frac{[\vec{e}_x \times \vec{q}_{\parallel}]}{q_{\parallel}} a_{q_{\perp}}^j \cdot \vec{v}_{\vec{p}} \right| n' \vec{p}' \right) \left(n\vec{p} \left| \frac{[\vec{e}_x \times \vec{q}_{\parallel}]}{q_{\parallel}} a_{q_{\perp}}^{j'} \cdot \vec{v}_{\vec{p}'} \right| n' \vec{p}' \right)^*$$

where $\varepsilon_{n\vec{p}}, f_{n\vec{p}}$ - dispersion laws and distribution functions for light ($n=l$) and heavy ($n=h$) holes respectively.

Given description for photon emission is applicable where the conditions

$$x \gg q_{\perp}^{-1}, l_{ph-p} \gg q_{\perp}^{-1} \quad (19)$$

are satisfied (l_{ph-p} - photon relaxation length in case of on-hole scattering).

The left hand inequality is satisfied where photons are registered in the far-field zone while the right hand inequality eliminates from consideration the term specifying on-hole photon relaxation.

4. FORMULA FOR FAR ZONE FIELD ENERGY

Let us consider the secondary quantized operator for Poynting's vector in symmetrized form:

$$\hat{\vec{S}} = i \left\{ \frac{c}{4\pi} \left[\hat{\vec{E}} \times \hat{\vec{H}} \right] - \frac{c}{4\pi} \left[\hat{\vec{H}} \times \hat{\vec{E}} \right] \right\} \quad (20)$$

The first term in (20) in view of (1a) is re-presentable in the following form:

$$\hat{\vec{S}}_{(1)} = -\frac{i\hbar}{4\pi} \sum_{\nu\nu'} \sqrt{\frac{\omega_{\nu'}}{\omega_{\nu}}} \left[\left(\mathbf{b}_{\nu} \text{rot } \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}} + \mathbf{b}_{\nu}^+ \text{rot } \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}*} \right) \times \left(\mathbf{b}_{\nu} \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}} - \mathbf{b}_{\nu}^+ \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}*} \right) \right] \quad (20a)$$

With a precision of the second order nonzero contribution (with respect to photon interaction) to the average value $\langle \hat{\vec{S}} \rangle$ will be only from $\langle \mathbf{b}_{\nu}^+ \mathbf{b}_{\nu'} \rangle$ and $\langle \mathbf{b}_{\nu} \mathbf{b}_{\nu'}^+ \rangle$;

from (20a) one may obtain:

$$\vec{S}_{(1)} = -\frac{i\hbar}{4\pi} \sum_{\nu\nu'} \sqrt{\frac{\omega_{\nu'}}{\omega_{\nu}}} \left\{ \langle \mathbf{b}_{\nu}^+ \mathbf{b}_{\nu'} \rangle \left[\text{rot } \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}*} \times \vec{a}_{\nu'}^{\vec{r}} \right] - \langle \mathbf{b}_{\nu} \mathbf{b}_{\nu'}^+ \rangle \left[\text{rot } \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}} \times \vec{a}_{\nu'}^{\vec{r}*} \right] \right\} \quad (21)$$

Similarly, let us examine the 2nd term in (20);

thus we obtain:

$$\vec{S}_{(2)} = -\frac{i\hbar}{4\pi} \sum_{\nu\nu'} \sqrt{\frac{\omega_{\nu'}}{\omega_{\nu}}} \left\{ -\langle \mathbf{b}_{\nu}^+ \mathbf{b}_{\nu'} \rangle \left[\vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}*} \times \text{rot } \vec{a}_{\nu'}^{\vec{r}} \right] + \langle \mathbf{b}_{\nu} \mathbf{b}_{\nu'}^+ \rangle \left[\vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}} \times \text{rot } \vec{a}_{\nu'}^{\vec{r}*} \right] \right\} \quad (22)$$

From (20) we get the average value for Poynting's vector operator in symmetrized form, which, when (21), (22) under approximation of photon mode macro occupancy [5] are taken into account, will have the following form:

$$\vec{S} = \frac{\hbar}{2\pi} \sum_{\nu\nu'} \sqrt{\frac{\omega_{\nu'}}{\omega_{\nu}}} \left\{ \left\langle b_{\nu}^{+} b_{\nu'} \right\rangle \left[\text{rot } \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}*} \times \vec{a}_{\nu'}^{\vec{r}} \right] - \left\langle b_{\nu'}^{+} b_{\nu} \right\rangle \left[\text{rot } \vec{a}_{\nu}^{\vec{r}} \times \vec{a}_{\nu'}^{\vec{r}*} \right] \right\} \quad (23)$$

Let us consider the radiation in $x < 0$ area. Using (23) with respect to (6) (in which we set $A_{+} = 0$) and (17a) we get:

$$\vec{S}^{(-)} = -\vec{e}_x \frac{\hbar}{2\pi \mathbf{v}_{\perp}} \sum_{j'j} \sum_{\vec{q}} L_{\vec{q}_{\parallel}, q_{\perp}}^{(p)jj'} \{f\} A_{-}^{j*} A_{-}^{j'} \quad (24)$$

Using (13), (15) (L -mode is excluded for it attenuates beyond the plate) and (18), let us compute (24) for Lattinger's isotropic model [6]. Now we get that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{S}^{(-)} &= -\vec{e}_x \frac{3}{\sqrt{2}\pi} \frac{e^2 \eta_-^{\frac{5}{2}}}{V \hbar^2 \mathbf{v}_\perp \varepsilon^s m^2} \sin^2 \theta \\
 \sum_{\vec{q}} \omega_q^{\frac{1}{2}} &\left\{ \left[k^2 (\bar{q} - \tilde{q})^2 + (k^2 - \bar{q}^2)(k^2 - \tilde{q}^2) \sin^2 kd \right] \frac{|a_l|^2}{\bar{q}^2 (k + \tilde{q})^2} + \frac{4k^2 |a_r|^2}{(k + \bar{q})^2} \right\}^2 \\
 &\left(\left\{ \frac{\exp \left[\frac{\hbar \omega_q \eta_-}{m_l} - \mu(T) \right]}{kT} + 1 \right\}^{-1} \left(1 - \left\{ \frac{\exp \left[\frac{\hbar \omega_q \eta_-}{m_h} - \mu(T) \right]}{kT} + 1 \right\}^{-1} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

$$\text{where } \theta = \overset{\wedge}{\vec{p}, \vec{p}'}, \quad \frac{1}{m_l} - \frac{1}{m_h} = \frac{1}{\eta_-}$$

Using (25), one can get

$$\oint S_n^{(-)} ds = \frac{3}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{e^2 \eta_-^{\frac{5}{2}} s}{V \hbar^2 \mathbf{v}_\perp \varepsilon^s m^2} \sin^2 \theta$$

$$\sum_{\bar{q}} \omega_q^{\frac{1}{2}} \left\{ \left[k^2 (\bar{q} - \tilde{q})^2 + (k^2 - \bar{q}^2)(k^2 - \tilde{q}^2) \sin^2 kd \right] \frac{|a_l|^2}{\bar{q}^2 (k + \tilde{q})^2} + \frac{4k^2 |a_r|^2}{(k + \bar{q})^2} \right\}^2$$

$$\left(\frac{\exp \left[\frac{\hbar \omega_q \eta_-}{m_l} - \mu(T) \right]}{kT} + 1 \right)^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{\exp \left[\frac{\hbar \omega_q \eta_-}{m_h} - \mu(T) \right]}{kT} + 1 \right)^{-1} \quad (26)$$

Thus, the theoretical study of semiconductors radiation for non-geometrical optics is conducted.

It is shown that the radiation is characterized by strongly marked peaks for resonance transmission as one can see from (26).

R E F E R E N C E S

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